

D. 7.3. Monitoring & Evaluation strategy

WP7 – Management and Coordination

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Abstract	This deliverable aims at presenting the gEnesys' project monitoring and evaluation strategy (M&E), namely to lay out the principles upon which the assessment of the project's activities, outcomes and outputs are based and the actions and instruments through which this assessment is performed. The evaluation is <i>forward-looking</i> , <i>formative</i> and intended to improve the project's activities as they unfold (thus, it is process-oriented). It is also aimed at making the consortium and the project more responsive to internal and external demands. By doing so, the M&E team will detect and solve possible bottlenecks and challenges before they can negatively affect the project's results.

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1. BACKGROUND OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable aims at presenting the gEnesys' project monitoring and evaluation strategy (M&E), namely to lay out the principles upon which the assessment of the project's activities, outcomes and outputs are based and the actions and instruments through which this assessment is performed. In the gEneSys project the M&E strategy is part of the WP7 (management and coordination) and is carried out by the coordination team and more specifically by those team members with an expertise in project evaluation. As a general principle, the evaluation activity sets to accompany the project during its entire life cycle. The evaluation is therefore *forward-looking*, *formative* and intended to improve the project's activities as they unfold (thus, it is process-oriented). It is also aimed at making the consortium and the project more responsive to internal and external demands. In this view, in addition to the planned report deliverable at M18 (mid-term M&E report) and M36 (final evaluation report), the strategy envisages the design of instruments to collect partners' and external stakeholders' feedbacks and a number of informal communications (both written and oral) to inform the partners about the progress of the projects. By doing so, the coordination team hopes to detect and solve possible bottlenecks and challenges before they can negatively affect the project's results. In this respect, the coordination team positions itself as a critical friend (Rallis and Rossman, 2000) who supports the work conducted by the partners whilst also challenging assumptions and misconceptions.

Building on these considerations, the evaluation team's task is threefold. Firstly, it will make sure that the project's reports and outputs are delivered as planned and that the stated objectives and deadlines of the project are met. Secondly, it will ensure that the tasks runs smoothly and in the full respect of the project's founding principles of transparency, mutual learning, collaboration and valorization of the competencies of all the participants (including senior and junior staff) as declared and agreed among partner organisations during the kick off meeting (see D 7.1.). Thirdly, the evaluation team will act as a 'sentinel' toward emerging phenomena and requests in the wider environment that may warrant a shift in the specific tasks and/or objectives. In this respect, the role of the stakeholders is paramount to stay abreast of the emergent tendencies and disruptions in the energy and green transition arena, which is the area of interest of the gEneSys project. Thus, the envisaged tasks will also involve activities to monitor and evaluate the level of the engagement of the external stakeholders (including also of the project's advisory board) in tandem with the gEneSys stakeholder engagement officer and the Communication and Dissemination WP Leader (P8- Portia). The M&E strategy of the gEneSys project will conform to the principles of the *relations-based evaluation framework* as set out by Pisacane and Tagliacozzo (2023). It will also be inspired by the recommendations emerged by the Expert Group on support for the *strategic coordinating process for partnerships* (EC, 2023) and by the Commission Staff Working's Document illustrating an *Evidence Framework on monitoring and evaluation of Horizon Europe* (European Commission, 2023)

The current deliverable is structured as follows. Alike many evaluation strategies, the current strategy starts from spelling out the gEneSys' general and specific objectives. This allows us to monitor the extent to which the project activities, outcomes and outputs are *directed towards the achievement of these objectives (directionality principle)*. Then, the gEneSys consortium is presented to highlight the challenges that may arise from the specific features of this consortium and illustrate how the M&E strategy plans to detect and prevent the emergence of these challenges. The gEneSys' stakeholders landscape is then briefly described. After this overview, the M&E strategy is articulated including the definition evaluation questions, indicators and evaluation instruments. Finally, the timeline of the M&E activities is explicated.

2. THE GENESYS PROJECT AND ITS OBJECTIVES

The gEneSys project stems from the assumption that the energy transition is a dynamic and mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem composed of several interacting subsystems including the technological, policy, social, environmental, governance, and economic ones. Each of these sub-systems has evident gendered connotations (e.g., in terms of production and use of the knowledge in the respective domains). However, the SDG7 (Energy access for all) has little to no references to these gendered implications and impacts. Thus, one of the main objectives of gEneSys is the following:

OBJECTIVE 1: gEneSys will cooperate with partners in Africa to demonstrate the gender concerns in the EU's and UN's mission to supply/ensure access to affordable and secure energy and show how to integrate gender perspectives into SDG7 for gender equality benefits

The analyses that will be carried out during the project aims also to highlight the role of intersectional aspects in determining how the energy transition impacts differently men and women and shape gender-related inequalities in different domains. Thus, the second objective states that:

OBJECTIVE 2: gEneSys will address the intersectional aspects of gender inequality through the analysis of existing data and by collecting, analysing, and theorising original data collected in the project through extensive surveys.

In addition to these intersectional aspects, gEneSys considers it relevant to examine the different roles (e.g., as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, employees and consumers) that women can take in the energy transition and how these roles can be affected by gender prejudices. Thus objective 3 delves into the following theme:

OBJECTIVE 3: gEneSys will examine available statistics on the participation and roles that women hold in energy related sectors as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and employees. It will also collect new data to understand the behaviours and attitudes to energy transition of women and men as citizens and consumers.

Furthermore, gEnesys recognizes that gender aspects are usually poorly factored in when analyzing the social dimensions and impacts of energy transition. Thus objective 4 states that:

OBJECTIVE 4 gEnesys will apply a gender lens to the social dimensions of the energy transition

In general, gEnesys considers that forging partnerships and collaborations with actors and stakeholders in the energy transition domain is a critical means for the achievement of gender equality in this sector. It follows that objective 5 declares that:

OBJECTIVE 5. gEnesys will promote international collaborations and engagement of the wider range of change actors and stakeholders in Europe and Africa to show the benefits of using gender equality as a lever in achieving sustainable socio-economic development

2.1. The gEnesys' partners, activities and outputs

The gEnesys project brings together 8 partners from five countries (Italy, Germany, UK, Poland and Rwanda). Although all the partner organisations share a research remit, their specific missions are diverse. For example, the National Research Council of Italy, that holds the role of Project coordinator, is the largest multidisciplinary research institution in Italy with institutes spread across all the Italian territory. Likewise, Fraunhofer is Europe's largest application-oriented research organization. The Jagiellonian University and the Imperial College are academic organizations with a mixed focus on research and teaching. ENEA – the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development – furnishes scientific and research-based advice to relevant Italian Ministries and it is an established expert in the energy transition sector, taking part also in other EU projects on this theme (e.g., ENTRANCES). PORTIA is a small and medium enterprise with a specific expertise on mainstreaming gender dimensions in research. Finally, AIMS - The African Institute for Mathematical Sciences - is a pan-African network of Centres of Excellence for post-graduate training in mathematical sciences, research and public engagement in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). In terms of geographical distribution, the consortium comprises two partners in Southern Europe (Italy), two in Central Europe (Germany), one in Eastern Europe (Poland), one in Northern Europe (UK) and one outside Europe (Rwanda). From a political perspective, two of the partners are located in non-EU countries (UK and Rwanda).

During the course of the 3 years project, these partners will be involved in performing several activities including:

1. Research-based tasks such as desk research, policy analysis, case study analysis, closed surveys, Delphi surveys, interviews etc. (WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5)
2. Promotion of gender sensitive education (WP3), including a summer school for PhD students and early career researchers (WP6)
3. Engagement with various stakeholder organisations such as sister projects, other similar initiatives, private and public energy utility companies etc (see

- the following subsection for an overview of the gEneSys stakeholder's landscape) (WP6, WP5, WP7)
4. Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions (WP5)

These activities will produce a number of deliverables and outputs which encompass reports presenting the results of the research activities, guidance notes for policymakers, policy briefs, recommendations for training programmes and toolboxes.

2.2. The gEneSys' stakeholder landscape

A stakeholder refers to any group or individual who has the potential to influence or be impacted by an organization's objectives and actions. The concept of stakeholder theory, originally proposed by Edward Freeman in 1984, suggests that corporations have responsibilities not only towards their financial shareholders but also towards employees, customers, suppliers, business partners, communities, and other entities affected by their operations. This idea has gained widespread acceptance and is now commonly used not only in the business world, but also in civil organization and academia.

Numerous studies have shown that the majority of leaders recognize their responsibilities towards multiple stakeholders, and many companies and organizations have implemented stakeholder consultation practices. Understanding the diverse stakeholders and their interests, as well as developing strategies to effectively engage with them, has become a crucial skill for corporate leaders. Today, considering and addressing the needs and concerns of various stakeholders has become an essential competency in corporate leadership, in project management and in politics.

To address this, it is crucial to conduct stakeholder mapping and subsequent stakeholder analysis. Stakeholder mapping involves identifying and categorizing all relevant stakeholders based on their level of interest and influence in the project. This process helps to determine the key stakeholders who should be actively engaged and considered in decision-making.

Stakeholder mapping is a systematic approach to identifying the key individuals or groups who have a vested interest in a particular project. This process involves identifying all the relevant stakeholders who may be affected by or have an influence on the project's outcomes. Stakeholders can range from individuals to larger groups, especially in the context of extensive projects.

After stakeholder mapping, stakeholder analysis is conducted to assess the interests, needs, expectations, and potential impacts of each stakeholder group. This analysis enables a deeper understanding of stakeholder perspectives, concerns, and potential contributions to the project. It also helps in formulating effective communication and engagement strategies to foster positive relationships and address any potential conflicts or challenges.

By conducting stakeholder mapping and analysis, project teams can make informed decisions, prioritize stakeholder engagement efforts, and ensure that the project's outcomes align with stakeholder interests and expectations. It promotes transparency, collaboration, and inclusivity in project planning and execution.

Stakeholder mapping plays a crucial role in ensuring the success of a project. Projects often involve numerous stakeholders, and mapping them out helps in effectively managing their expectations.

By identifying and mapping the stakeholders, project managers can engage with them and gain valuable insights. The input and feedback provided by stakeholders can be instrumental in achieving a successful project outcome.

Active engagement with stakeholders also contributes to a higher perception of success. When stakeholders' expectations are properly managed through stakeholder mapping, they are more likely to view the project as a success.

In summary, stakeholder mapping is essential for project success as it enables better expectation management, facilitates valuable stakeholder engagement, and increases the overall perception of project success.

As part of the project, we will assess and include a comprehensive stakeholder map in Deliverable 6.3., ensuring a thorough and accurate representation of all relevant stakeholders.

We have currently identified various stakeholders, including:

- Sister projects (e.g., Leap - Re);
- Other initiatives addressing the role of women in the energy sector (e.g. EUI, Lights on women).
- Energy communities;
- Policy makers and national ministries.

3. MONITORING AND EVALUATION STRATEGY

3.1. Evaluation dimensions and questions

The current M&E strategy is part of the T7.5 which runs during all the life course of the project. Given what has been described in the sections above, the strategy will revolve around three key dimensions, touching both internal and external aspects. Here we describe the evaluation dimensions and we explicate the evaluation questions that sit under each dimension.

EVALUATION DIMENSION 1. *Internal Relationships' Management.* This dimension is intended to gather insights into the functioning of the gEneSys consortium and anticipate and resolve potential bottlenecks induced by conflicts and divergent interests and working practices among partners that may hinder the achievement of

the project's objectives (Pisacane & Tagliacozzo, 2023). Overall, this M&E dimension seeks to respond to the following evaluation questions:

1. How well do participants collaborate by sharing knowledge, information and resources?
2. How well is the consortium able to adapt its organisational practices to the changeable circumstances and demands coming from the inside and outside of the network?
3. To what extent are participants able to manage conflicts and tensions while remaining respectful of the divergent working practices and organisational priorities?
4. How well is the coordinating structure able to manage diversity and heterogeneity within the network?
5. How well can the participants manage the individual and shared resources made available by the network (i.e. time, lessons, money, staff)?
6. (6) To what extent does the project foster EU integration and international cooperation?
7. (7) To what extent have early career researchers been involved in the project activities?

EVALUATION DIMENSION 2. Internal – Project activities and outputs.

This evaluation dimension gathers information about the extent to which the project objectives as stated in section 2 are achieved through the delivery of the project's outcomes and outputs and about the perceptions of partners regarding the project's implementation. It also takes into consideration the added value of the projects' outputs for the stakeholders and the society at large (additionality principle) (European Commission, 2023). Overall, this evaluation dimension seeks to respond to the following questions:

1. Were the project's outputs delivered on time?
2. Did the project's activities and outputs fulfill the objectives set for the project?
3. Did the project's outputs add new elements to the existing scientific knowledge and policy debate?
4. To what extent are the partners and the whole consortium able to translate scientific and technical information into knowledge understandable by policymakers and the society at large?
5. To what extent have the project's key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of the partner organisations, beyond the genesys project?
6. To what extent are the resources provided for the project (e.g. budget, time, guidance) perceived as sufficient by partner organisations?

EVALUATION DIMENSION 3 – External – stakeholder engagement

This third evaluation dimension seeks to explore the extent to which the consortium engages with relevant stakeholders and builds relationships that may help in disseminating project's results.

1. To what extent do partner organisations create new ties with external stakeholders?
2. To what extent are the project's activities and outputs perceived as relevant by the external stakeholders?
3. To what extent are the project's results disseminated among the external stakeholders?
4. To what extent are the stakeholders committed to or aligned with sustainable practices and long-term project's objectives?

3.2. Evaluation indicators and means of verification

Some of the evaluation dimensions mentioned above seek also to monitor the emerge and reduce the impact of the potential risks identified at the proposal stage (see, for example Risk 2 "Unforeseen events/conflicts or disputes among partners"). Many of the risks related to partners not delivering timely or to difficulties in securing the collaboration of external experts to complete the project's tasks will be minimized through the constant engagement of partners and external stakeholders and the monitoring of these activities.

Table 1 - Below provides details on the indicators and means of evaluation for each of the identified questions.

Dimension	Questions	Indicators	Means of evaluation
1. Internal Relationships' Management	How well partners collaborate by sharing knowledge, information and resources	1.a Perception of bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium	Surveys to all the participants
	How well is the consortium able to adapt its organisational practices to the changeable circumstances and demands coming from the inside and outside of the network	1.b Perception of responsiveness and adaptability to internal changes	Surveys to all the participants
		1.c Perception of responsiveness and adaptability to external changes and demands	
	To what extent are participants able to manage conflicts and tensions	1.d Frequency to which different working practices created bottlenecks in the project's activities	Surveys to all the participants
	How well is the coordinating structure able to manage	1.e Perceived ability of the coordinating organization to	Surveys to all the participants

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Dimension	Questions	Indicators	Means of evaluation
	diversity and heterogeneity within the network	manage internal relationships	
	How well can the participants manage the individual and shared resources made available by the network (i.e. time, lessons, money, staff)?	1.f Perceived ability to make use of the resources made available within the network	Surveys to all the participants
	To what extent do partners perceive to get benefits from being part of the consortium	1.g Perceived benefits deriving from being part of the consortium	Surveys to all the participants
	To what extent does the project foster EU integration and international cooperation?	1.h Increase of the perceived benefits coming from pan-European cooperation	Surveys to all the participants
		1.i Perceived collaboration/power hierarchies between partners from different European regions	
		1.l Perceived integration of non EU-partner in the project's activities	
	To what extent have early career researchers been involved in the project activities?	1.m Number of early career researchers working on project activities	Survey to team leaders
		1.n Number of deliverables where an early career research appear as author	Review of deliverables
		1.o Number of training/networking opportunities for early career researchers	Survey to team leaders
Internal – Project activities and outputs.	Were the project's outputs and tasks delivered on time	2.a Number of deliverables submitted as planned	Review of deliverables and tasks
	Did the project's activities and outputs	2.b Number and type of project's objectives fulfilled by each output	Review of the outputs produced by the project

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Questions</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Means of evaluation</i>
	fulfill the objectives set for the project?		Surveys to advisory board members
	Did the project's outputs add new elements to the existing scientific knowledge and policy debate?	2.c Perceived added value	Survey to advisory board members
		2.d Number of scientific publications produced	Review of the scientific publications produced
	To what extent is the project consortium able to translate scientific and technical knowledge into information that can be understood and used by policymakers and by the society at large?	2.e Number of policy briefs and policy documents produced	Review of outputs
		2.f Number of materials produced for public outreach	Review of outputs
	To what extent have the project's key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of the partner organisations, beyond the genesys project?	2.g Perceived integration of key themes into other research streams	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent are the resources provided for the project (e.g. budget, time, guidance) perceived as sufficient by partner organisations?	2.h Perceived efficiency of the project	Survey to team leaders
3.External – stakeholder engagement	To what extent do partner organisations create new ties with external stakeholders?	3.a Number and type of new connections created outside the consortium	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent are the project's activities and outputs perceived as relevant by the external stakeholders?	3.b Perceived relevance by external stakeholders	Survey to external stakeholders

Dimension	Questions	Indicators	Means of evaluation
	To what extent are the project's results disseminated among the external stakeholders?	3.c Number of dissemination activities performed	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent are the stakeholders committed to or aligned with sustainable practices and long-term project's objectives?	3.d Number of meetings, workshops, or conferences attended during the project and at the end.	Excel form to send to all the external stakeholders.
		3.e Monitor the extent and tone of media coverage related to the project through social media.	Excel form to send to all the external stakeholders.

3.3. Design Of Evaluation Instruments

Three different instruments will be constructed to perform the M&E task.

- Firstly, an *excel sheet* will be set up to perform the review activity. The *excel sheet* will contain the tasks and deliverables planned and will be used to determine whether they have been delivered on time (indicator #2a) and which project's objectives they fulfill (indicator # 2b). The excel sheet will also be used to track the number of scientific publications (indicator 2d) and of documents for policymakers and the general public produced during the course of the project (indicator 2e and 2f)
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- An *online survey* will be created on Google form to collect inputs from partner organizations. This survey will have two versions, one for all the participants mostly asking feedbacks about the functioning of the consortium (dimension 1). A more extended version will be forwarded to team leaders only to gather information about, among others, the staff working within each team, the type of new ties created by the research group and the research streams beyond the gEneSys project. The survey will contain both closed ended and open-ended questions.
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- An *online survey* will be created on Google form to collect inputs from the advisory board members and the external stakeholders. Again, the external stakeholders survey will be shorter and more focused compared to that administered to advisory board members. Selected external stakeholders will be contacted at an earlier stage to collect their consent to receive the survey and provide feedback about the project.

Finally, we plan to start the collection of the information for some indicators (such as those concerning the deliverables and outputs produced) from April 2024 to allow the time for the project to deliver meaningful outcomes.

3.4. Timeline Of Monitoring and Evaluation Activities

The survey to partner organizations will be sent out every 6 months, to allow for a regular monitoring of possible barriers to the implementation of the activities. Likewise, the excel sheet will be completed by the M&E team every 6 months. Another survey will be forwarded to advisory the board members and external stakeholders every 12 months. Figure 1 show the proposed timeline of M&E activities.

Proposed timeline for the M&E activities

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This M&E strategy is intended to deliver a comprehensive overview of the project's progress in a range of areas, spanning from the internal functioning of the consortium to the project's outcomes, outputs and added value. To this end, we have set a plan for collecting, on a regular basis, feedback from different sources, including partners and external stakeholders. Implicit to the successful implementation of these activities, is the ability to actively listen to the voices of these actors and integrate their suggestions and comments into the project's activities with the intent to enhance them.

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